

THE PREVALENCE OF INTESTINAL NEMATODE IN SCHOOL CHILDREN IN EBONYI LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA, EBONYI STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to determine the prevalence of intestinal nematodes infection in school children between February and April 2009. Eight hundred fecal samples were examined using direct smear method. Of this number, 204 (25.5%) infected with the parasites of intestinal nematodes were *Ascaris lumbricoides* (20.0%), *Strongyloides stercoralis*, (0.4%) Hookworm (3.5%) and *Trichuris trichuria* (1.3%) implicated. Sex was found to be a strong factor influencing their prevalence. Chi square test with statistical significance difference ($p < 0.05$) was used for the analysis. The study revealed that *Ascaris lumbricoides* had the highest prevalence of infection among the parasites implicated. However, regular deworming exercise with albendazole and other possible diagnosis methods will improve the health status of the infected children. Personal hygiene and health campaign programmes should be carried out to the general public on the importance of control and possible eradication of the parasite.

KEYWORDS: Prevalence, intestinal helminthes, parasites, nematode.

Introduction

Intestinal nematodes are members of the phylum nematoda which varies in order but with successful group consisting of small worms which occupy essentially every habitat in which multicellular organisms can survive (Crompton, *et al* 1989). There are worldwide public health infection threat that affects up to one billion people in under developed nations of the tropics and subtropics. Intestinal helminthes infection seems the most common among school age children and tends to be high in the age group (5-15) (Albonico *et al*, 1999). Despite considerable advances in chemotherapy and control, intestinal nematode infections rank among the most wide spread of soil transmitted parasites that affects significant proportion of the world. The disease can affect child developments, education achievements, reproductive health and economic development (Saviolil *et al*, 2004). The epidemiology of infection is dependent on three interactive factors, which includes the suitability of the environment for the eggs and larval development, the mode and extent of fecal pollution on the soil, the mode and extent of contact between infected soil and skin and the presence or absence of abiotic factors on the viability of oval development (Brooker and Micheal, 2000). School health programmes have been identified as a cost effective strategy to control morbidity due to soil transmitted helminthes like *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichuria* and hookworms in school-age groups (Hotez *et al*, 2005). According to World Bank (1993), human intestinal parasites cause significant mortality and morbidity in underdeveloped countries especially in children. In this study area, the disease is more prevalent among the lower class and peasant farmers who are likely to come in contact with the contaminated soil while working outdoors. Also children who play and have contact with the contaminated soil and work bare footed are more prone to infection. Indiscriminate disposal of human and animal faeces, poor personal hygiene and inadequate good water supply could also be attributed to high level of soil transmitted helminthic infections (Odikamnor and Ike, 2004).

Intestinal obstruction, anemia, malnutrition, dysentery, fever, dehydration, vomiting colitis cognitive and other impairments are major complication associated with soil transmitted helminthes infections (Baron, 2003). Thus, its infection seems been domesticated in the area of this research because of their constant and close contact with the soil as well acquiring infections. Poor and unhygienic water and food sources as routes of infection when ingested, illiteracy or the public health importance of wearing foot wears and eating/ drinking treated water and food which are obviously lacking in this area as significant factors influencing the high level of soil helminthes infections as also stated by Asaolu *et al*, (1991) Human becomes infected by ingesting infective eggs of the parasite or by infective larvae penetrating the skin before becoming adult which later migrate through the hearts and lungs for about 10 days. The infection is caused when contaminated food or water with embryonated

oocysts are ingested, thousand of eggs are laid by the worms daily and there are passed in the faeces of the infected hosts (Mabosa *et al.*, 2004) The eggs mature in the soil and ingestion of feacally contaminated soil can also become source of infection where children are the most vulnerable. Then, penetration of skin by infected larvae also plays a role in a case of hookworm (De Silva *et al.*,1995)

This research was geared toward determining the prevalence of intestinal nematodes in school pupils in Ebonyi local Government Area, Ebonyi State.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area.

The study was conducted in Ebonyi local government Area of Ebonyi State, located in the North zone of the State, South Eastern Nigeria. The climate is predominated with rain forest and annual rain fall of about 1600mm and average atmospheric temperature of 30°C which are the two distinctive seasons. The area is traversed by a number of streams and rivers which are marked by fairly thick vegetations. Basic social amenities are totally lacking with no or poor proper sewage system in most communities. Farming and trading are the major occupation of inhabitants of this area with low educational status dominating the population.

Study Population

Eight hundred (800) samples were examined from three (3) schools selected in Ebonyi Local Government Area. Of this number, 300, 450 and 50 were covered from each schools respectively but was observed that the toilet facilities of the two in one private school. Compliance of the pupils was made possible through the combined effort of the head teachers who acknowledged the letter of introductory from team of researchers.

Laboratory Analysis

Faecal samples were collected from pupils of each school and analyzed differently, and those that were not analyzed the same day of collection were preserved with 10% formalin solution. Faecal sample analysis was performed using parasitological method as described by Cheesbrough (1998). For intestinal helminthes diagnosis, various methods could be employed which may include direct stool smear, formal-ether concentration and floatation method.

These methods are used in hospital and scientific laboratories in developing countries due its affordable nature, simplicity and sensitivity. But for this research, direct smear method were used for the identification of eggs of intestinal helminthes.

Microscopic Examination

- (a) Wet mount: this is used to detect the presence of eggs, protozoa trophozoites and cysts. It can also reveal the presence of RBC, and WBCs.
- (b) Iodine wet mount: it is used to stain glycogen and nuclei of the cysts.

Procedure

About 0.1g of faeces was collected with an applicator stick and emulsified on a drop of normal saline placed on the labeled glass slide. The smear was made sufficiently thin so that the cover slip does not float on it. The preparation was then covered with clear cover slip to avoid air bubbles. The slide was then mounted and examined for parasite eggs under x10 objective of the microscope.

Statistical Analysis

Chi square test was used to test for an association between all pairs of nematode parasite infection and gender of children for each sex group. Statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) was achieved with intensity of helminthes infection as measured by the mean of (eggs per gram) epg count.

RESULTS

Out of eight hundred faecal samples examined 204 (25.5 99%) had soil transmitted helminthes infection. These include 395 males and 405 females. Four intestinal helminthes identified were *Ascaris lumbricoides* (20.0%), hook worm (3.5%), *Trichuris trichuria* (1.6%), *Strongyloides stercoralis* (0.4%).

Table 1 reveals the prevalence of intestinal nematode infections by sex of pupil. It shows that 395 and 405 samples were examined for the parasites egg. The males where more infected with 109(27.6%) followed by the

females with 95 (32.5%95%). The relationship between sexes was not significantly different with highest prevalence in male.

The prevalence of intestinal nematode based on parasite types shows that out of four organisms investigated among the eight hundred samples examined, *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Strongyloides stercoralis*, hookworm and *Trichuris trichuria*. This shows that *Ascaris lumbricoides* has the highest number of infection with 162 followed by Hook worm with 28 samples infected respectively Table 2.

Table 1: Prevalence of Intestinal Nematode Infection by Sex of Pupil

Sex	No examined	No infected	<i>Ascaris</i>	<i>Trichuris</i>	<i>Strongyloides</i>	Hookworm
Male	395	109	86(21.8%)	8(2.00)	3(0.8%)	16(4.10)
Female	405	95	74(18.3%)	4(0.99)	0(0.0)	12(2.86)

The prevalence based on toilet types suspected to be used by the pupils from which they might have acquired the infections shows that 15 pupils used water

closet system with no infection recorded, 425 pupils used bush method with 150 infections and 360 pupils used pit toilet with 54 infections respectively Table 3.

Table 2: Prevalence Based on Types of Parasites.

S/N	Intestinal nematode	No: of sample examined	No: infected	% age
1	<i>Ascaris</i>	800	160	20.0
2	<i>Strongyloides</i>	800	3	0.4
3	Hookworm	800	28	3.5
4	<i>Trichuris</i>	800	12	1.6

Table 3: Prevalence Based on Type of Toilet

S/N	Toilet type	Total No examined	Total No infected	% Age
1	Water closet	15	0	0
2	Bush method	425	150	35.3
3	Pit toilet	360	54	15.0
	Total	800	204	25.5%

DISCUSSION

Intestinal nematodes are those soil transmitted helminthes which have been considered as emerging public health problem. But in Ebonyi Local Government its prevalence could be attributed to poor people living in unhygienic environments or the disease is more prevalent among the lower class and peasant farmers who are likely to come in contact with the contaminated soil while working outdoors.

The investigation revealed that eight hundred pupils were examined for the prevalence of the parasites with two hundred and four pupils infected which ranges from *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Strongyloides stercoralis*, hookworm and *Trichuris trichuria* respectively.

The prevalence of intestinal nematode infection by sex of pupils revealed that out of eight hundred samples examined for the parasites, it was observed that one hundred and nine(109)(27.69) males out of 395 sampled were infected and out of four hundred and five females sampled, only ninety five (23.59) were infected. This shows that the prevalence of intestinal nematode infection is high in males than their female counter part. This could be as a result of the facts that children whose parents are peasant farmers often go to farm with their male children which were found frequently with barefoot. This may lead to more accumulation of infections than

their female counter part as they come in contact with the contaminated soil which may lead to penetration of the larvae of soil transmitted helminthes. This synchronizes with the work by Odikamnor and Ikeh (2004), Ukpai and Ugwu (2003) which states that intestinal nematodes are nematode diseases that affect especially local farmers and poor people as there are traced with unhygienic environments and contaminated soil.

Furthermore, the analysis on the type of parasites revealed that, out of four (4) organisms implicated from fecal sample, *Ascaris lumbricoides* was recorded with high prevalence of 160 (20.0%) infection and is assumed to be predominant among other organisms. This could be attributed with the fact that *Ascaris lumbricoides* were much higher in their water or food (raw vegetables) which the farmers consume or ingest not considering the hygienic level of the food material which are been eaten in farm yards and homes. This is in line with the work done by Bundy *et al.*, (1995) and Stephenson *et al.*, (1993) which states that *Ascaris lumbricoides* were much common with ingestion of water and food contaminated with *Ascaris lumbricoides* eggs and occasionally via inhalation of contaminated dust. Also similar with Naish *et al* (2004) which states that ova of *Ascaris lumbricoides* can survive a prolonged period of 10years under a warm, shady and moist environmental condition which could be a reason for their long constant infection.

Henceforth, the prevalence based on the type of toilet system used by pupils states that those that used bush method type of toilet recorded highest with 150 (35.3%) infected than those that used water closet and pit toilet respectively. this could be that bush method type of toileting, encourages the development of eggs and larvae of these soil transmitted helminthes infection. this occurs with indiscriminate defecation of fecal materials which creates a conducive atmosphere for the survival of eggs and larvae of these parasites. This agrees with Oyerinde (1999) which states that children constantly are infected hence they come in close contact with soil and use unwashed hands to eat, thus there is oral fecal contamination.

CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATION

However, no or less emphasis and sensitization on good personal and environmental hygiene are routes of contacting parasitic infections in this area.

Absolutely, worm burden and non deworming exercise are major causes of soil transmitted infections in rural area like this, as these diseases are attributed to poverty, peasant farmers and indiscriminate disposal of fecal materials which contributes to re-infections of intestinal helminthes. Therefore government should run to the aids of people in this area towards providing good water scheme, construct water system type of toilet (water closet) and advertise the importance of deworming exercise of children in this area. Improve their habitation, sanitation, access to health services and spring up campaign charged with important factors responsible for decreasing the prevalence of parasitic infections as well, ensure the availability of albendazole for the treatment of infected people.

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